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4 Taming the smallest predators of the oceans
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7 Javier del Campo^{1*}, Fabrice Not^{1,2}, Irene Forn¹, Michael E. Sieracki³ and Ramon Massana¹

8
9 ¹ *Department of Marine Biology and Oceanography, Institut de Ciències del Mar, CSIC.*

10 *Barcelona, Catalonia, Spain.*

11 ² *Marine Plankton Group, UMR7144 Station Biologique de Roscoff, CNRS-UPMC, Roscoff,*

12 *France*

13 ³ *Bigelow Laboratory for Ocean Sciences, East Boothbay, Maine, USA.*

14
15 **Corresponding: Department of Marine Biology and Oceanography, Institut de Ciències del*

16 *Mar (CSIC), Passeig Marítim de la Barceloneta 37-49, 08003 Barcelona, Catalonia, Spain.*

17 *Phone: 34-93-2309500; Fax: 34-93-2309555; E-mail: jdelcampo@ibe.upf-csic.es*

19 **Abstract**

20 Protists (unicellular eukaryotes) arguably account for most eukaryotic diversity and are
21 central players of the biosphere. Known protist diversity and biology is largely based on
22 cultured strains. Yet, environmental molecular surveys have unveiled entirely novel lineages
23 that, as their prokaryotic counterparts, are essentially uncultured. Culture bias is an important
24 drawback for any microbe related science and is particularly severe for heterotrophic protists,
25 which depend on organic food sources for growth. Here we show how ecologically significant
26 bacterivorous protists have been brought into culture by mimicking *in situ* conditions. Single
27 cells sorted by serial dilution or flow cytometry were inoculated into seawater amended with
28 natural bacterial assemblage at nearly *in situ* abundances. Strains belonging to lineages only
29 known so far from environmental sequencing were isolated. Among them, *Minorisa minuta*
30 gen. nov. sp. nov. forms a novel branch within Rhizaria, holding a key evolutionary position,
31 and with an average size of 1.4 μm represents one of the smallest bacterial grazers known to
32 date. It has a worldwide planktonic distribution and can account for 5% of heterotrophic
33 protists communities in coastal waters. Physiological features of this strain can partly explain
34 its success in the environment. Culturing ecologically relevant but elusive protists provide
35 invaluable material for ecophysiology, genomics, ecosystem modeling, and evolutionary
36 issues.

37 **Keywords:** culture / isolation / single cell / chlorarachnea / novelty / heterotrophic flagellates

38 **Introduction**

39 Unicellular organisms are major forces driving our planet ecosystems and are an outstanding
40 reservoir of biological diversity (genes, molecules, metabolic pathways, and cellular
41 processes) yet to be discovered (Falkowski *et al.*, 2008). They are also main actors in macro-
42 and microevolutionary processes for life on Earth (Cavalier-Smith and Chao, 2006).
43 Nowadays, culture independent approaches are regularly applied to investigate the diversity
44 and function of microbes in the environment. Despite the valuable information provided by
45 “omics” environmental studies, culture bias definitely remains as one of the most critical
46 challenges faced by scientists aiming to achieve a full understanding of the ecological role of
47 microbes (Giovannoni *et al.*, 2007a) and is currently a bottleneck in ecosystem studies
48 (Giovannoni *et al.*, 2007b; Raes and Bork, 2008). Environmental DNA surveys demonstrate
49 the extent to which culturing efforts poorly capture *in situ* microbial diversity (Pedrós-Alió,
50 2006). Many lineages unveiled in the last few years and holding key phylogenetic positions to
51 understand macroevolutionary patterns among eukaryotes are essentially composed of
52 environmental sequences (Epstein and López-García, 2008). It is estimated that as little as 0.1
53 to 1% of bacterial and protist cells can be easily cultured (Caron *et al.*, 1989; Amann *et al.*,
54 1995). Unfortunately, some of the most highly represented taxa in the environment have not
55 been cultured yet and some of those in culture do not appear to be among the most abundant
56 (Massana *et al.*, 2004; Sherr *et al.*, 2007). Consequently, ultrastructural, physiological and
57 genomic information for many ecologically relevant microorganisms is missing.

58 This culture bias can be overcome by using original culturing strategies (Button *et al.*, 1993),
59 as demonstrated for prokaryotes like *Candidatus Pelagibacter ubique* and *Nitrosopumilus*
60 *marinus* (Rappé *et al.*, 2002; Könneke *et al.*, 2005), both initially detected through
61 environmental molecular surveys and later identified as ecologically relevant taxa. *Candidatus*

62 *Pelagibacter ubique* was brought into culture by mimicking oligotrophic conditions and
63 *Nitrosopumilus marinus* were cultured in media amended with ammonia once molecular data
64 revealed they were ammonia oxidizers. Similar culturing efforts have seldom been applied to
65 marine protists, even though culture bias is perceived as a major limitation to investigate
66 further the functional role and ecological significance of photosynthetic protists (Vaulot *et al.*,
67 2008), being even more severe for the heterotrophic ones (Jürgens and Massana, 2008).

68 Marine heterotrophic flagellates perform key processes in microbial food webs as bacterial
69 grazers, trophic linkers, and nutrient remineralizers (Sherr and Sherr, 2002; Pernthaler, 2005).
70 They exhibit a variety of trophic strategies and constitute a diverse assemblage of poorly
71 identified species (Arndt *et al.*, 2000; Vaulot *et al.*, 2002). Up to now, bacterivorous
72 flagellates have been invariably cultured using rich media composed of seawater
73 supplemented with rice grains or yeast extract that promote the growth of very large bacteria
74 at very high densities. This strategy inexorably retrieves the same species complexes (i.e.
75 *Cafeteria*, *Paraphysomonas*, or *Neobodo* spp.) that are known to be rare in marine plankton
76 (Jürgens and Massana, 2008). Abundant taxa identified by molecular surveys still remain
77 uncultured, for example the bacterivorous MAST clades (Massana *et al.*, 2006a).

78 In order to bring into culture ecologically relevant heterotrophic flagellates, we mimicked
79 oligotrophic marine conditions by amending sterile seawater with a mix of natural bacteria
80 collected from the same sampling site at abundances only slightly higher than *in situ*. To this
81 media we added a single heterotrophic flagellate cell retrieved by dilution or by flow
82 cytometry. This approach enabled us to obtain several interesting precultures. Some of them
83 were stabilized and maintained for months as stable cultures allowing its phylogenetic,
84 morphological and ecological characterization.

85

86 **Material and Methods**

87 *Isolation by single cell dilution*

88 Samples were collected at the Blanes Bay Microbial Observatory on the 25th of September
89 2007. Forty liters were filtered by gravity through 3 μm and incubated at 20°C in the dark for
90 two days. Then, this incubated sample was filtered by 0.45 μm and bacteria in the filtrate
91 were concentrated by tangential flow filtration. Bacterial concentrates were quantified by
92 epifluorescence microscopy using DAPI staining (Porter *et al.*, 1980) (typically ca 10⁸ cells
93 mL⁻¹) and kept frozen. Multi-well plates of 0.1 or 1 mL were filled with aged seawater (3 μm
94 filtered seawater kept in the dark for 2 months, 0.2 μm filtered and autoclaved before use),
95 and an aliquot of the concentrate was added to attain a final concentration of 5 x 10⁶ bacteria
96 mL⁻¹. Heterotrophic flagellates from the same 2-days incubated sample were counted by
97 epifluorescence microscopy after DAPI staining and diluted to add one cell per well. Plates
98 were incubated at 20°C in the dark and inspected for flagellate growth by inverted microscopy
99 every three days during a period of three weeks. Wells with observed growth were scaled to
100 30 mL to establish a pre-culture and later a stable culture.

101 *Isolation by single cell sorting*

102 Seawater from a second sampling (30th of September 2008) was filtered through 3 μm , and
103 sent to Bigelow Laboratory for Ocean Sciences (Boothbay Harbor, ME, USA) for cell sorting
104 in a MoFlo™ Flow Cytometer (Dako-Cytomation, Denmark). Digestive vacuoles of
105 heterotrophic protists were stained using the vital stain LysoTracker® (Life Technologies, NY,
106 USA) and cells were sorted based on their green fluorescence (LysoTracker® fluorescence)
107 and the absence of chlorophyll fluorescence. Details of the staining protocol and flow
108 cytometer setup are described elsewhere (Rose *et al.*, 2004; Heywood *et al.*, 2011). Side

109 scatter was used to select only the smallest protists, approximately $<10\ \mu\text{m}$ in diameter.
110 Individual target cells were deposited into 24-well plates, in which some wells were dedicated
111 for positive controls (10 cells per well) and negative controls (0 cells per well). All wells on
112 the microplates contained 1ml aged seawater together with natural bacteria as before. Multi-
113 well plates were sent back to the Institut de Ciències del Mar (Barcelona, Catalonia, Spain) by
114 plane at room temperature (12 hours) and treated as above.

115 *Culture maintenance*

116 Cultures were maintained in 50 mL flasks and transferred every 2 to 4 weeks to fresh media
117 (aged sea water with added bacteria as described above) at 1/10 dilution. The full culturing
118 protocol is outlined in Supplementary Fig. 1. Physiological parameters were inferred from a
119 batch culture where the abundance of flagellates and bacteria were followed twice a day by
120 epifluorescence microscopy after DAPI staining. Growth rate was calculated from the
121 exponential increase of flagellate cells. Grazing rate was calculated using the exponential
122 decrease of bacterial cells and the average concentration of flagellates and bacteria during the
123 incubation (calculated according to Frost 1972). Growth efficiency was calculated from the
124 ratio of protist biomass produced as compared with bacterial biomass consumed.

125 *Sequencing and phylogenetic analysis*

126 For molecular analysis, the whole culture was filtered on $0.6\ \mu\text{m}$ polycarbonate filters, DNA
127 was extracted by standard procedures, and 18S rDNA genes were PCR amplified with
128 eukaryote-specific primers (Díez *et al.*, 2001). Complete sequences of 18S rDNA were
129 obtained with five internal primers by the MACROGEN Genomics Sequencing Services
130 (accession numbers XXXXXXXX – XXXXXXXX). Sequences were identified and inspected
131 for chimeras by BLAST and KeyDNATools (<http://www.keydnatools.com>) and were aligned
132 with a subset of relative sequences using MAFFT (Kato et al., 2002). Alignments were

133 checked with Seaview 3.2 (Galtier *et al.*, 1996) and highly variable regions of the alignment
134 were removed using Gblocks (Castresana, 2000). Maximum likelihood (ML) phylogenetic
135 trees were constructed with the fast ML method RAxML (Stamatakis, 2006) using the
136 evolutionary model GTRMIXI. Phylogenetic analyses were done in the freely available
137 University of Oslo Bioportal (www.bioportal.uio.no). Repeated runs on distinct starting trees
138 were carried out to select the tree with the best topology (the one having the best Likelihood
139 of 1000 alternative trees). Bootstrap ML analysis was done with 1000 pseudo-replicates and
140 the consensus tree was computed with MrBayes (Huelsenbeck and Ronquist, 2001).

141 *Scanning Electron Microscopy*

142 Scanning Electron Microscopy was performed as in Garcés *et al.* (2006). Samples were fixed
143 for 2h in 2% OsO₄ diluted in seawater, or with 2% glutaraldehyde. Cells were subsequently
144 washed with distilled water (2 h) and filtered onto a 0.6 μm pore size Nuclepore™ filter
145 (Whatman, Maidstone, UK). Samples were dehydrated in an ethanol series (30, 50, 70, 96,
146 and 100%) for 15 min each, followed by an acetone series (25, 50, 75, and 100%) for 15 min
147 each. Samples were critical point-dried in liquid CO₂ using a BAL-TEC CPD 030 critical
148 point drying apparatus (Balzers Union, Balzers, Germany). Filters were subsequently glued to
149 SEM-stubs with colloidal silver, sputter coated with gold palladium, and examined with a
150 Hitachi S-3500N (Nissei Sangyo Co. Ltd., Tokyo, Japan) SEM operating at 5 kV.

151 *TSA-FISH analysis (Tyramide Signal Amplification-Fluorescent in situ Hybridization)*

152 Samples were fixed with formaldehyde (2% final concentration), filtered on 0.6 μm pore size
153 Nucleopore filters and kept frozen. The probe CRN02 (5'-TACTTAGCTCTCAGAACC-3')
154 was designed with the ARB package (Ludwig *et al.*, 2004) to have no mismatches with the
155 target sequences (coverage in Fig. 1a) and at least two mismatches with non-target sequences.
156 The probe was purchased with a 5' aminolink (C6) from Thermo Fisher Scientific and was

157 labeled with the enzyme horseradish peroxidase, HRP (Roche Diagnostic Boehringer) as
158 described elsewhere (Urdea *et al.*, 1988; Amann *et al.*, 1992). The hybridization was carried
159 out on filter pieces using the temperatures and conditions described in Not *et al.* (2002). The
160 signal amplification was done using a tyramide (as the substrate of HRP) labeled with Alexa
161 488 as in Pernthaler *et al.* (2004). The probe was tested against the positive culture in a
162 gradient of formamide (10 to 70%) in the hybridization buffer. Optimized conditions were
163 35°C and 30% formamide in the buffer. The probe gave a negative signal with several non-
164 target cultures. Filters were counterstained with DAPI, mounted in a slide with an oil mix
165 containing Vecta Shield, and observed by epifluorescence microscopy at 1000 x under UV
166 (DAPI signal) and blue light excitation (TSA-FISH signal). Two transects (of around 15 mm)
167 were inspected per filter piece. Counts for Blanes samples were done triplicated (standard
168 errors were typically 20% of the mean) whereas no replicates were done for the worldwide
169 and culture samples. The minimal abundance quantified by this counting strategy was around
170 1 cell ml⁻¹.

171

172 **Results**

173 Pre-cultures based on serial dilution yielded a 5.2% success rate (growth observed in 25 of the
174 480 inoculated wells). Out of the 25 pre-cultures, 12 were stable and were scaled to 30 mL
175 volumes. Based on their 18S rDNA, 4 pre-cultures were identified as *Paraphysomonas* spp.
176 and the others represented taxa closer to environmental sequences than to any known culture,
177 including a cercozoan, a rhizarian (two pre-cultures), a choanoflagellate, a chrysophyte, two
178 unclassified stramenopiles, and a MAST (Table 1). After a second step of single cell
179 inoculation from the latter 8 flasks, some pre-cultures were lost and others were substituted by
180 a different cell type. The two resulting unieukaryote clonal and stable cultures included a

181 rhizaria related to chlorarachniophytes (Fig. 1a) and a stramenopile distantly related to
182 *Developayella elegans* (Supplementary Fig. 2). Single cell sorting by flow cytometry was
183 carried out to avoid time-consuming serial dilution steps. From the 400 wells inoculated using
184 single cell sorting, growth was detected in 5 wells (1.25% success rate). All of them were
185 identified as the same rhizarian lineage obtained by the dilution method. Scanning electron
186 microscopy performed on the two stable cultures revealed extremely small cells with little
187 morphological features (Fig. 1b and Supplementary Fig. 3). Based on these SEM images we
188 observed that rhizarian cells (40 cells measured) had one flagellum and measured 0.8-2 μm in
189 width (mean of 1.3 μm , standard deviation of 0.4) and 1.0–2.1 μm in length (mean of 1.5 μm ,
190 SD= 0.4) whereas *Developayella*-like cells (13 cells measured) had two flagella (one with
191 hairs) and measured 1.2-3 μm in width (mean of 2.1 μm , SD=0.6) and 1.5-3.0 μm in length
192 (mean of 2.3 μm , SD= 0.5).

193 The rhizarian isolate was distant to any described organism, its 18S rDNA sequence being
194 only 90.6% similar to *Chlorarachnion reptans*. The 18S rDNA sequence of our isolate was
195 highly similar to environmental sequences retrieved from the Mediterranean Sea
196 (BL000921.31 and BL010625.12; Massana *et al.*, 2004), the Sargasso Sea (SSRPE06; Not *et*
197 *al.*, 2007), and the English Channel (RA070625T.047; Marie *et al.*, 2002). Therefore, we
198 decided to focus in the rhizarian isolate for the rest of our study, given its taxonomic novelty
199 and its similarity with environmental marine sequences. This small heterotrophic flagellate
200 has been named *Minorisa minuta* gen. nov. sp. nov. (see formal description at the end of this
201 section).

202 Following *Minorisa minuta* abundance and that of the bacterial prey for several days in a
203 batch culture has assessed its physiological properties. This flagellate grew relatively fast on
204 natural bacteria (doubling time of 10.6 hours) and reduced bacterial abundances from 10^7 cells

205 mL⁻¹ to around 10⁶ cells mL⁻¹ (Fig. 1c). The estimated growth efficiency (bacterial biomass
206 converted to protist biomass) of this protist in this batch culture was 30%, and its grazing rate
207 was 7 bacteria flagellate⁻¹ h⁻¹.

208 *Minorisa minuta* was a significant component of marine heterotrophic flagellates on a global
209 scale, being both widely distributed and abundant (Fig. 2a). TSA-FISH counts using a newly
210 designed specific probe revealed abundances up to 60 cells mL⁻¹ (17 cells mL⁻¹ on average) in
211 the Atlantic, Pacific, Indian, and Southern Oceans and the Mediterranean Sea. It accounted
212 for 1.8% of heterotrophic flagellates in these samples, a value that increased to 5% when
213 considering coastal sites only (Table 2). *Minorisa minuta* was detected all year long in a
214 coastal oligotrophic station in the NW Mediterranean Sea (Fig. 2b), ranging from 12 to 120
215 cells mL⁻¹ (52 cells mL⁻¹ on average) and accounting for 1 to 12% of heterotrophic flagellates
216 (5% on average). In this site, its abundance was well correlated with bacterial cells numbers
217 (Fig. 3a). Sizing *Minorisa minuta* cells in natural marine assemblages using TSA-FISH
218 observations confirmed its picoeukaryotic character with cell size varying from 1 to 3 μm
219 (Fig. 3b).

220 *Minorisa minuta* J. del Campo gen. nov. sp. nov.

221 Naked and spherical or ovoid cells: 0.8-2 μm (mean = 1.3) in width and 1.0-2.1 μm (mean =
222 1.5) in length. They possess a single flagella that could be as long as four times the cell
223 length. They are swimmers and active bacterial grazers.

224 Holotype: Fig. 1b from culture BMO.6.C1, isolated from Blanes Bay Microbial Observatory
225 (NW Mediterranean Sea) and maintained at the Institut de Ciències del Mar (Barcelona,
226 Catalonia, Spain). Scanning microscopy samples and FISH samples are also preserved there.
227 18S rDNA sequence deposited in GenBank under accession number: XXXXXX.

228 Etymology: Latin *Minorisa*, Manresa, author's born town. Latin *minuta*, tiny, refers to the
229 small size of the organisms.

230 Type locality: Blanes Bay (Catalonia, Spain)

231 Habitat and ecology: In Blanes Bay, the organism was detected in coastal plankton all year
232 long. It has been also detected in different world oceans, but the maximum abundances have
233 always been observed in coastal areas.

234

235 **Discussion**

236 Using the culturing approach developed here, we isolated several small heterotrophic
237 flagellates belonging to previously uncultured taxa and from distant lineages within the
238 eukaryotic tree of life (Table 1). When applied at different temporal and spatial scales, this
239 strategy will potentially give access to a wealth of novel heterotrophic protists in culture. This
240 is important because the presence of heterotrophic flagellates in culture collections is scarce
241 (Gachon *et al.*, 2007), and among the ones present in culture collections there are few with a
242 significant representation in the environment (Lim *et al.*, 1999).

243 The tiny unflagellated *Minorisa minuta* stands up as one of the smallest bacterivore known so
244 far, together with the minuscule phagotrophic bicosoecid *Symbiomonas scintillans* isolated
245 from open oligotrophic waters (Guillou *et al.*, 1999). Moreover, it represents the only
246 heterotrophic representative within the chlorarachniophytes, the single photosynthetic lineage
247 within rhizaria. Chlorarachniophytes are marine amoeboid flagellated cercozoans (Cavalier
248 Smith and Chao, 2003) that together with the Euglenophytes represent the two unrelated
249 eukaryotic groups that acquired a chloroplast by secondary endosymbiosis with a green alga
250 (Delwiche, 1999). The discovery of this unpigmented protist could be another evidence

251 indicating that the acquisition of the green chloroplast took place independently in both
252 lineages (Rogers *et al.*, 2007). Nevertheless, this is not a definitive clue since the absence of
253 chloroplast could also derive from a posterior loss of it. Therefore, the genome analysis of
254 *Minorisa minuta* is of primary interest to study the transition to secondary plastid
255 endosymbiosis and, as for its photosynthetic counterparts in the oceans, is expected to reveal
256 unprecedented cellular, biochemical, and evolutionary pathways (Worden *et al.*, 2009).

257 We have shown here that *Minorisa minuta* has a worldwide marine distribution and is a
258 significant member of heterotrophic flagellate assemblages, particularly in coastal waters. In
259 the same set of samples considered for the present study, *Minorisa minuta* followed in
260 abundance the uncultured MAST-4, MAST-1C and MAST-1B groups (Massana *et al.*,
261 2006a), which is remarkable given that its probe is clearly more specific than MAST probes
262 (roughly species versus family level). Our data suggest that the importance of this organism in
263 coastal waters is comparable to the importance of MAST in open waters, considered as
264 abundant bacterivores in the sea. *Minorisa minuta* represents one of the main players in the
265 eukaryotic picoplankton of coastal ecosystems, possibly having a relevant role in the carbon
266 fluxes and in controlling bacterial populations. Nevertheless, many more samples need to be
267 processed in order to verify the patterns of its abundance, distribution and coastal preference.
268 Its growth rate is double of that observed in MAST in unamended incubations (Massana *et*
269 *al.*, 2006b), and similar to or lower than maximal growth rates observed for other cultured
270 heterotrophic flagellates (Eccleston-Parry and Leadbeater, 1994, Boenigk *et al.*, 2007). The
271 estimated growth efficiency and its grazing rate are again within the range of known cultured
272 strains. The functional response of *Minuta minuta* exhibits a half-saturation constant much
273 lower than that of other cultured flagellates, below 10^6 cells mL⁻¹ (Rodríguez-Martínez in
274 prep.). This suggests that this grazer is adapted to live at the usual bacterioplankton
275 concentrations in marine waters. The physiological properties of *Minorisa minuta* can explain

276 its ecological success and set this species as a good example of dominant marine
277 heterotrophic flagellates (Montagnes *et al.*, 2012), whose parameters could be used to
278 improve ecological models (Caron *et al.*, 2009). New experiments must be performed in order
279 to determine its functional behavior and the degree of its influence over the coastal microbial
280 community.

281 This is the first time that a widely distributed and abundant heterotrophic flagellate has been
282 obtained in culture. Getting the environmentally relevant bacteria *Candidatus Pelagibacter*
283 *ubique* in culture led to a leap forward towards a better understating of microbes' function in
284 the oceans and opened up several research directions (Tripp *et al.*, 2008). Taming small
285 marine predators with ecological relevance holds promise for similar future discoveries.

286

287 **Acknowledgements**

288 This study was supported by projects MICROVIS (CTM2007-62140/MAR, MEC), FLAME
289 (CGL2010-16304, MICINN) and BioMarKs (2008-6530, ERA-net Biodiversa, EU). JdC was
290 funded by the I3P program (I3PPRE-06-00676, CSIC) and FN by the Marie-Curie fellowship
291 ESUMAST (MEIF-CT-2005-025000). We thank Marco Álvarez for help in TSA-FISH,
292 Vanessa Balagué for help in molecular analysis and Nicole Poulton for help in flow
293 cytometry.

294

295 **References**

296 Amann RI, Zarda B, Stahl DA, Schleifer KH. (1992). Identification of individual prokaryotic
297 cells by using enzyme-labeled, rRNA-targeted oligonucleotide probes. *Appl Environ*
298 *Microbiol* **58**: 3007-3011.

299 Amann RI, Ludwig W, Schleifer KH. (1995). Phylogenetic identification and in situ detection
300 of individual microbial cells without cultivation. *Microbiol Rev* **59**: 143-169.

301 Arndt H, Dietrich D, Auer B, Cleven EJ, Gräfenhan T, Weitere M, *et al.* (2000). Functional
302 diversity of heterotrophic flagellates in aquatic ecosystems. In: Leadbeater BSC, Green JC
303 (Eds) *The Flagellates: Unity, Diversity and Evolution*. Taylor & Francis Group, London, UK,
304 **pp 240-268**.

305 Boenigk J, Jost S, Stoeck T, Garstecki T. (2007). Differential thermal adaptation of clonal
306 strains of a protist morphospecies originating from different climatic zones. *Environ*
307 *Microbiol* **9**: 593-602.

308 Button DK, Schut F, Quang P, Martin R, Robertson BR (1993). Viability and isolation of
309 marine bacteria by dilution culture: theory, procedures and initial results. *Appl Environ*
310 *Microbiol* **59**: 881-891.

311 Caron DA, Davis PG, Sieburth JMcN. (1989). Factors responsible for the differences in
312 cultural estimates and direct microscopical counts of populations of bacterivorous
313 microflagellates. *Microb Ecol* **18**: 89-104.

314 Caron DA, Worden AZ, Countway PD, Demir E, Heidelberg KB. (2009). Protists are
315 microbes too: a perspective. *ISME J* **3**: 4-12.

316 Cavalier-Smith T, Chao EEY. (2003). Phylogeny and classification of phylum cercozoa
317 (Protozoa). *Protist* **154**: 341-358.

318 Cavalier-Smith T, Chao EEY. (2006). Phylogeny and megasystematics of phagotrophic
319 heterokonts (Kingdom Chromista). *J Mol Evol* **62**: 388-420.

320 del Campo J, Massana R. (2011). Emerging diversity within chrysophytes, choanoflagellates
321 and bicosoecids based on molecular surveys. *Protist* **162**: 435-448.

322 Delwiche C. (1999). Tracing the thread of plastid diversity through the tapestry of life. *Am*
323 *Nat* **154**: S164-S177.

324 Díez B, Pedrós-Alió C, Massana R. (2001). Study of genetic diversity of eukaryotic
325 picoplankton in different oceanic regions by small-subunit rRNA gene cloning and
326 sequencing. *Appl Environ Microbiol* **67**: 2932-2941.

327 Eccleston-Parry JD, Leadbeater BSC. (1994). A comparison of the growth kinetics of six
328 marine heterotrophic nanoflagellates fed with one bacterial species. *Mar Ecol Prog Ser* **105**:
329 167-177.

330 Epstein S, López-García P. (2008). “Missing” protists: a molecular prospective. *Biodivers*
331 *Conserv* **8**: 27-42.

332 Falkowski PG, Fenchel T, Delong EF. (2008). The microbial engines that drive Earth’s
333 biogeochemical cycles. *Science* **320**: 1034-1039.

334 Frost BW. (1972). Effects of size and concentration of food particles on the feeding behavior
335 of the marine planktonic copepod *Calanus pacificus*. *Limnol Oceanogr* **17**: 805-815.

336 Gachon CMM, Day JG, Campbell CN, Pröschold T, Saxon RJ, Küpper FC. (2007). The
337 Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa (CCAP): a biological resource for protistan
338 genomics. *Gene* **406**: 51-57.

339 Garcés E, Fernandez M, Penna A, Van Lenning K, Gutierrez A, Camp J. (2006).
340 Characterization of NW Mediterranean *Karlodinium* spp. (Dinophyceae) strains using
341 morphological, molecular, chemical, and physiological methodologies. *J Phycol* **42**: 1096-
342 1112.

343 Giovannoni SJ, Foster RA, Rappé MS, Epstein S. (2007). New cultivation strategies bring
344 more microbial plankton species into the laboratory. *Oceanography* **20**: 62-69.

345 Giovannoni SJ, Stingl U. (2007). The importance of culturing bacterioplankton in the ‘omics’
346 age. *Nature Rev Microbiol* **5**: 820-826.

347 Guillou L, Chrétiennot-Dinet MJ, Boulben S, Moon-van der Staay SY, Vaultot D. (1999).
348 *Symbiomonas scintillans* gen. et sp. nov. and *Picophagus flagellatus* gen. et sp. nov.
349 (Heterokonta): two new heterotrophic flagellates of picoplanktonic size. *Protist* **150**: 383-398.

350 Heywood JL, Sieracki ME, Bellows W, Poulton NJ, Stepanauskas R. (2011). Capturing
351 diversity of marine heterotrophic protists: one cell at a time. *ISME J* **5**: 674-684.

352 Jürgens K, Massana R. (2008). Protistan grazing on marine bacterioplankton. In: Kirchman,
353 DL (Ed.) *Microbial Ecology of the Oceans*, Second Edition. John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New
354 York, USA, pp **383-441**.

355 Könneke M, Bernhard AE, de la Torre JR, Walker CB, Waterbury JB, Stahl DA. (2005).
356 Isolation of an autotrophic ammonia-oxidizing marine archaeon. *Nature* **437**: 543-546.

357 Lim EL, Dennet MR, Caron DA (1999). The ecology of *Paraphysomonas imperforata* based
358 on studies employing oligonucleotide probe identification in coastal water samples and
359 enrichment cultures. *Limnol Oceanogr* **44**: 37-51.

360 Ludwig W, Strunk O, Westram R, Richter L, Meier H, Yadhukumar, *et al.* (2004). ARB: a
361 software environment for sequence data. *Nucleic Acids Res* **32**: 1363-1671.

362 Massana R, Balagué V, Guillou L, Pedrós-Alió C. (2004). Picoeukaryotic diversity in an
363 oligotrophic coastal site studied by molecular and culturing approaches. *FEMS Microbiol*
364 *Ecol* **50**: 231-243.

365 Massana R, Terrado R, Forn I, Lovejoy C, Pedrós-Alió C. (2006a). Distribution and
366 abundance of uncultured heterotrophic flagellates in the world oceans. *Environ Microbiol* **8**:
367 1515-1522.

368 Massana R, Guillou L, Terrado R, Forn I, Pedrós-Alió C. (2006b). Growth of uncultured
369 heterotrophic flagellates in unamended seawater incubations. *Aquat Microb Ecol* **45**: 171-180.

370 Montagnes D, Roberts E, Lukeš J, Lowe C. (2012). The rise of model protozoa. *Trends*
371 *Microbiol* **20**: 184-191.

372 Not F, Simon N, Biegala IC, Vaultot D. (2002). Application of fluorescent *in situ*
373 hybridization coupled with tyramide signal amplification (FISH-TSA) to assess eukaryotic
374 picoplankton composition. *Aquat Microb Ecol* **28**: 157-166.

375 Not F, Gausling R, Azam F, Heidelberg JF, Worden AZ. (2007). Vertical distribution of
376 picoeukaryotic diversity in the Sargasso Sea. *Environ Microbiol* **9**: 1233-1252.

377 Pedrós-Alió C. (2006). Marine microbial diversity: can it be determined? *Trends Microbiol*
378 **14**: 257-263.

379 Pernthaler A, Pernthaler J, Amann R. (2004). Sensitive multicolor fluorescence *in situ*
380 hybridization for the identification of environmental microorganisms. In: Akkermans ADL,

381 de Bruijn FJ, van Elsas JD. (Eds) *Molecular Microbial Ecology Manual*, Second Edition.
382 Kluwer Academic Publishers, Dordrecht, Netherlands, **pp 711-726**.

383 Pernthaler J. (2005). Predation on prokaryotes in the water column and its ecological
384 implications. *Nature Rev Microbiol* **3**: 537-546.

385 Porter KG, Feig YS. (1980). The use of DAPI for identifying and counting aquatic microflora.
386 *Limnol Oceanogr* **25**: 943-948.

387 Raes J, Bork P. (2008). Molecular eco-systems biology: towards an understanding of
388 community function. *Nature Rev Microbiol* **6**: 683-699.

389 Rappé MS, Connon SA, Vergin KL, Giovannoni SJ. (2002). Cultivation of the ubiquitous
390 SAR11 marine bacterioplankton clade. *Nature* **418**: 630-633.

391 Rogers MB, Gilson PR, Su V, McFadden GI, Keeling PJ. (2007). The complete chloroplast
392 genome of the chlorarachniophyte *Bigeloviella natans*: evidence for independent origins of
393 chlorarachniophyte and euglenid secondary endosymbionts. *Mol Biol Evol* **24**: 54-62.

394 Rose JM, Caron DA, Sieracki ME, Poulton NJ. (2004). Counting heterotrophic
395 nanoplanktonic protists in cultures and aquatic communities by flow cytometry. *Aquat Microb*
396 *Ecol* **34**: 263-277.

397 Sherr EB, Sherr BF. (2002). Significance of predation by protists in aquatic microbial food
398 webs. *Anton van Leeuwen* **81**: 293-308.

399 Sherr BF, Sherr EB, Caron DA, Vaultot D. (2007). Oceanic protists. *Oceanography* **20**: 130-
400 134.

401 Tripp HJ, Kitner JB, Schwalbach, MS, Dacey JWH, Wilhelm LJ, Giovannoni SJ. (2008).
402 SAR11 marine bacteria require exogenous reduced sulphur for growth. *Nature* **452**: 741-744.

403 Urdea MS, Warner BD, Running JA, Stempien M, Clyne J, Horn T. (1988). A comparison of
404 non-radioisotopic hybridization assay methods using fluorescent, chemiluminescent, and
405 enzyme labeled oligodeoxyribonucleotide probes. *Nucleic Acids Res* **16**: 4937-4956.

406 Vaultot D, Romari K, Not F. (2002). Are autotrophs less diverse than heterotrophs in marine
407 picoplankton? *Trends Microbiol* **10**: 266-267.

408 Vaultot D, Eikrem W, Viprey M, Moreau H. (2008). The diversity of small eukaryotic
409 phytoplankton ($\leq 3\mu\text{m}$) in marine ecosystems. *FEMS Microbiol Ecol* **32**: 795-820.

410 Worden AZ, Lee JH, Mock T, Rouz P, Simmons MP, Aerts AL, *et al.* (2009). Green
411 evolution and dynamic adaptations revealed by genomes of the marine picoeukaryotes
412 *Micromonas*. *Science* **324**: 268-272.

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420 **Figure legends**

421 **Figure 1 (a)** Maximum likelihood phylogenetic tree with complete 18S rDNA sequences
422 showing the position of *Minorisa minuta* within the Cercozoa. The scale bar indicates 0.1
423 substitutions per position. The coverage of the specific probe CRN02 is shown in blue. **(b)**
424 SEM image of a *Minorisa minuta* cell of 1.6 μm in size and possessing a single flagellum. **(c)**
425 Growth of *Minorisa minuta* with natural bacteria as prey in a batch culture.

426 **Figure 2 (a)** Abundances of *Minorisa minuta* cells at various sampling sites as estimated by
427 TSA-FISH counts. **(b)** Abundances of *Minorisa minuta* cells during a temporal study at
428 Blanes Bay (year 2007) together with the abundance of heterotrophic flagellates estimated by
429 epifluorescence (log scale). Bars represent the contribution (in %) of *Minorisa minuta* cells to
430 heterotrophic flagellates.

431 **Figure 3 (a)** Correlation between the abundances of *Minorisa minuta* and natural bacteria
432 during the seasonal study (year 2007) at Blanes Bay. **(b)** Cell size distribution of *Minorisa*
433 *minuta* in these samples (1148 cells measured by TSA-FISH).

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435 **Supplementary Information**

436 **Figure 1** Isolation protocol flow chart.

437 **Figure 2** Maximum likelihood phylogenetic tree with complete 18S rDNA sequences
438 showing the position of *Developayella*-like isolate within the stramenopiles. Environmental
439 sequences are in bold. The scale bar indicates 0.1 substitutions per position.

440 **Figure 3** Additional SEM pictures of the two stable cultures.

Table 1. Taxonomic affiliation of the obtained pre-cultures and stable pure cultures based on blast similarity (march 2012).

	Closest cultured match	%	Lineage	Closest match	%
<i>Pre-cultures</i>					
• Rhizaria					
IE1.2.D2	<i>Chlorarachnion reptans</i>	90.5	chlorarachniophyte	SSRPE06	99.8
IE1.4.B4	<i>Chlorarachnion reptans</i>	90.9	chlorarachniophyte	SSRPE06	99.9
IE4.4.A1*	Cercozoa sp. CC-2009d	94.4	cercozoan	SA2.4G8	96.8
• Opisthokonta					
IE1.4.D1	<i>Stephanoecca cauliculata</i>	91.6	choanoflagellate	band 4DB38	97.7
• Stramenopiles					
IE1.1.A5	<i>Paraphysomonas foraminifera</i>	99.4	chrysophyte		
IE1.3.B3	<i>Paraphysomonas imperforata</i>	99.4	chrysophyte		
IE1.3.B6	<i>Developayella elegans</i>	94.4	stramenopile	RM2-SGM49	96.6
IE1.4.D5**	<i>Pseudobodo tremulans</i>	95.7	bicosoecida	Biosope_T123.046	95.7
IE2.4.A6*	Chrysophyceae sp. CCMP2296	91.5	chrysophyte	CD8.S17	98.8
IE3.4.B1	<i>Bolidomonas pacifica</i>	88.3	MAST-3	NIF.1E11	97.0
IE4.6.B5	<i>Paraphysomonas imperforata</i>	98.7	chrysophyte		
IE4.8.C6	<i>Paraphysomonas imperforata</i>	99.9	chrysophyte		
<i>Stable cultures</i>					
• Rhizaria					
<i>Minorisa minuta</i> ***	<i>Chlorarachnion reptans</i>	99.6	chlorarachniophyte	SSRPE06	99.6
• Stramenopiles					
Developayella-like	<i>Developayella elegans</i>	94.4	stramenopile	RM2-SGM49	96.6

* Sequences with ambiguities.

** Lost after one year of being stable.

*** Culture isolated by Flow Cytometry.

Table 2. Counts of *Minorisa minuta* (cells ml⁻¹) in a set of samples from diverse oceans and comparison with the counts of heterotrophic flagellates (cells ml⁻¹). Data of heterotrophic flagellates and codes of samples are from Massana *et al.* (2006a).

System	Date	<i>Minorisa minuta</i>	Heterotrophic flagellates	%- <i>Minorisa minuta</i>
Atlantic Ocean				
ATL1	24-aug-02	4	652	0.7
ATL2	27-aug-02	9	1003	0.9
ATL3	29-aug-02	9	584	1.6
ATL4	23-sep-02	54	1302	4.1
ATL5	30-sep-02	13	814	1.6
ATL6	12-jul-04	9	214	4.1
ATL7	15-jul-04	0	443	0.0
ATL8	30-jul-04	0	593	0.0
Pacific Ocean				
PAC1	09-may-02	12	-	-
PAC2	15-may-02	0.0	-	-
PAC3	18-may-02	60	-	-
Indian Ocean				
INO1	16-may-03	33	687	4.9
INO2	23-may-03	0	626	0.0
INO3	06-jun-03	5	719	0.7
Southern Ocean				
ANT1	03-dec-02	7	1562	0.4
ANT2	05-dec-02	4	1668	0.3
ANT3	11-dec-02	2	2367	0.1
Mediterranean Sea				
BL07	2007*	52	1039	5.0

*Average of a whole year samplig.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

a

b

Cell size distribution